

LINGUA-POETIC ANALYSIS OF AMERICAN AND UZBEK STORIES

M.Y. Kakharova

PhD teacher at Bukhara State University

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Abstract. *This article explores a lingua-poetic analysis of two short stories, "The Night-Born" by Jack London and "Jonfigon" by A. Qahhor; it also analyses different narrative structures, thematic elements in the context of American and Uzbek literature. The article highlights the unity of form and content in stories showing writers' linguistic style to show the emotional state of their protagonists. The comparative study of American and Uzbek stories is crucial to describe as it showcases the distinct socio-cultural influences developing storytelling traditions in American and Uzbek literature.*

Keywords: *conflicts, component, content, form, artistic details, lingua-poetics, structure, exposition, plot, lexemes.*

INTRODUCTION.

The author focuses on showing the characters' emotional state and their actions in a brief and concise way. The plot component that drives the development of events is the story's climax. The climax of the story reveals the most important point of the unfolding events. The resolution of the emerging problem helps bring about the solution. The following characteristics are defined as specific features of a short story in literature: 1. Place and time. 2. The state of artistic details and the vivid description of event details. 3. The introduction of characters that brings about the story's climax.

The number of characters in a short story can sometimes be one or more; the greater the number of characters, the more efforts should be required to reveal the problem in the climax of the story.

The plot – is a set of events depicted in a literary work, and the author uses the plot to delineate life. Some literary scholars consider the plot to be a sequence of events consisting of characters, which form both the structure and content of the story, while other scholars interpret the plot as a form. [1] The plot, as a set of events embodying life's contradictions, shows conflicts, sympathies, and antipathies between the characters of the literary work.

The famous playwright N. Pogodin stated: "The plot consists of the main conflict, a simple natural connection of life events and contradictions that arise from the essence of the content of a literary work." [2]

Jack London used the "The-Five-Act-Structure" for the plot in most of his works in American literature:

Exposition – In "The Night-Born," Jack London provided initial information about the protagonist, Trefethan. The story starts with Trefethan's telling his friends about his experiences at the old Alta-Inyo Club. A memorable event in Trefethan's life occurred in 1898 when he was a young, strong, and handsome man. He worked as a mining engineer in Klondike. Driven by the temptation of gold prospecting, the protagonist boasted about the money he had in his pocket and

he told to his friends that his heart was empty. Trefethan wanted to explain to his listeners why he has never got married until now.

Rising action – the emergence of the protagonist's goals and desires in life can drive the events of the story to develop quickly. Having settled down in Goldstead, a major turning point occurred in Trefethan's life. He walked to the East along the river through the large valley; while crossing the American Canyon, he noticed the smoke from a campfire. Trefethan encountered a group of Indian tribes, and here he met a woman named Lucy for the first time. The development of events in the story began with the protagonist's finding his love from a distant place. Trefethan realized that the reason for the freedom and serenity in the land of the Indian tribe was because of this woman, Lucy. Lucy was the leader of the tribe; she had been living in this tribe's shelter for a long time.

Climax – the most important part of the story is determined by Lucy's telling Trefethan about her adventures: listening to life-stories of the woman who had lived with the dream of an ideal life was very important for the protagonist. Lucy had been struggling for her freedom for a long time; she had a desire to live in the valleys and she wanted to be friends with otters and marigolds, and she liked to watch animal life. When Lucy's family went bankrupt, she began working in a factory and later she worked as a waitress in a restaurant. When she was 18, she got married to a man who dreamed of opening a restaurant and this denoted the end of her dreams. However, Lucy continued to dream of a joyful, free life, lamenting that her entire life had passed washing dishes in a tavern. Ultimately, Lucy realized that her husband Junon's filthy tavern was not for her and she escaped from that dirty life to distant places.

METHODOLOGY.

Comparative Literary Analysis: a comparative approach shows to analyze the similarities and discrepancies in the narrative techniques and thematic focus of the two stories. This includes comparing the depiction of personal struggles and character transformation in *The Night-Born* (American literature) and *Jonfigon* (Uzbek literature).

Character Analysis: A thorough analysis of protagonists in both stories is conducted to denote the motivations, emotional states, and the evolution of characters in the plot of stories. This includes studying the protagonist (Trefethan in *The Night-Born* and Jonfigon in *Jonfigon*) and their relationships with other key characters (Lucy in *The Night-Born* and Malohatkxon in *Jonfigon*). The study also focuses on how the development of these protagonists reflects broader social issues, such as the pursuit of freedom, personal happiness, and gender roles.

Narrative Structure Analysis: The study also compares plot structures of the two stories, focusing on the use of the five-act plot structure (Exposition, Rising Action, Climax, Falling Action, Resolution) in *The Night-Born* and the narrative progression in *Jonfigon*. This includes analyzing how the sequence of events in both stories drives character development and reflects the conflicts central to the narrative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Another event in the story *The Night-Born* plays an important role in the main hero's life. One day Lucy became separated from her companions and she was left alone on an unknown island. Lucy spotted the skeletons of eight horses in a tree; each horse had a saddle, and between the bones, there were bags. Firstly, she found the skin of a deer and, then she discovered gold, inside the bags. Having become the owner of pure gold, the adventurous life of the woman reached its peak.

Falling action – The events in the story “The Night-Born” show a decline in intensity when Lucy confessed her feelings to Trefethan. She proposed to marry her and live together as a family. However, Trefethan rejected Lucy's proposal.

Resolution – The final part of the story “The Night-Born” denoted how the protagonist had become a lonely and unhappy person. Trefethan regretted about his life, feeling that he could have lived a different life, closer to nature. In the end, he became an unhappy person due to his impulsiveness, with no difference from a reclusive old man.

In Uzbek literature, the plot can be both a form and a content in lingua-poetics. The plot of A. Qahhor's “Jonfigon” also consists of these components:

Exposition – The story “Jonfigon” began with the introduction of the protagonist, Jonfigon, who was described as someone who would cry out his sorrows in the street. Jonfigon was revealed to be a man who used to not beat his wife but he was extremely jealous. Before revealing Jonfigon's family conflicts to the reader, the writer provided initial information about the protagonist through the voices of other characters: Jonfigon was a protagonist who being drunk, grabbed someone passing in the street and said, – What am I to do? – and later he set fire to his own beard and cursed the person who gave a match to him.” [3]

Denouement – causes conflicts between the characters in the plot. The denouement serves as an impulse for quick development of events in a literary work. Readers can immerse themselves in the unfolding of the story. Having heard the cry of a woman, three or four people passing by the street entered the yard of Jonfigon, they tried to understand the cause of the family dispute in the short story of "Jonfigon,". It turns out that the reason of argument was Jonfigon's burning all his wife's (Malohatkhon) clothes in the fire. Finally, the couple even decided to put an end to their marriage.

The development of events refers to the expansion of the plot in the story. After trying to work at various jobs, Malohatkhon's husband did not approve of any of them. He dismissed one job saying, "It has no income except its salary; the products are too cheap, and by adding a penny to them, I won't be able to accumulate wealth." He left several jobs without any valid reason.

The climax in the story "Jonfigon" is when, despite obstacles, Malohatkhon, after first working as a janitor and then attending a driving course, drove a truck and became one of the most famous women in the city, winning three awards in two years. This represented the main hero's achievement of her dream.

The resolution denotes the conclusion of the characters' conflicts between one another. Jonfigon did not have a desire to divorce with his wife, so he promised the witnesses of the event that he would find a permanent job. By this way, the quarrel and disagreement in a common Uzbek family came to an end.

The stories "The Night-Born" and "Jonfigon" can be observed to adhere to the principles of unity of content and form in lingua-poetics. In "The Night-Born," Jack London portrayed the character of Trefethan, a strong, adventurous engineer who enjoyed traveling. Jack London conveyed how the young man became an unhappy person due to his impulsiveness and inability to express his love for the woman he adored, using the single word "jellyfish" to symbolize this. This demonstrates the adherence to the unity of form and content in the story.

The words and word combinations specific to the protagonist of Trefethan, include: "huge, gross mass of oscillating protoplasm, never married, stranger, coward." Moreover, phrases like "the general tiredness and staleness and fatness all the collapse and ruin of a man who had once

been strong but who had lived too easily and too well" [4] are used with lexemes that perfectly coincides with the protagonist. The meaning of these lexemes is as follows: "once a strong, robust young man, now turned into a dull, life-weary person."

In the story "The Night-Born," the deuteragonist, Lucy, is associated with the following words and word collocations: "dead sober, she runs like a wild thing, a night-born, she wants to run naked in the moonlight." Jack London prefers to depict the beautiful scenic view of nature before Trefethan met Lucy for the first time:

"It was a noble valley, now shut in by high canyon walls, and again opening out into beautiful stretches, wide and long, with pasture shoulder-high in the bottoms, meadows dotted with flowers, and with clumps of timber spruce – virgin and magnificent. The dogs were packing on their backs, and were sore-footed and played out; while I was looking for any bunch of Indians to get sleds and drivers from and go on with the first snow. It was late fall, but the way those flowers persisted surprised me. I was supposed to be in sub-arctic America, and high up among the buttresses of the Rockies, and yet there was that everlasting spread of flowers."[5]

Abdulla Qahhor was able to portray social issues through family issues in "Jonfigon". It is clear that attention has been given to the unity of form and content in the story. The writer set an example of the 20th century woman who without complaining about her husband's unemployment, was the bread-and-butter for her family (Malohatkxon). The form of the story was depended on the writer's ability to choose lexemes that coincided with the characters. Specifically, the writer used simple words and phrases that fit Jonfig'on, one of the 20th-century men who are ashamed of their wives working: *"It has no income compared to salary," "Would they give a horse and a camel for her reward?" "Malohat will leave me now,"* and so on.

A.Qahhor used unique expressions and word collocations for Malohatkxon: "Oh, dear, I don't need your money, just work". These expressions and word collocations reflect the respect and patience towards one's husband that are characteristic features of all Uzbek women.

CONCLUSION.

The lingua-poetic analysis of the stories ("The Night-Born") and "Jonfigon" can be analyzed according to the following principles: 1. The unity of time and place. The story begins in 1898, with the protagonist's experiencing unexpected events while wandering around Klondike in search of gold. The final part of the story covers the protagonist's life in the 1910s, with events continuing at the Alta-Inyo Club in San Francisco. The protagonist recounts his experiences to his relatives, expressing regret for the mistakes he had made in his life. ("The Night-Born")

The events in the story "Jonfigon" take place in an Uzbek family in the 20th century. Having heard a woman's crying, three people enter Jonfigon's yard. They saw Jonfigon burn his wife's clothes in the bonfire.

2. The unity of form and content: The main concept of the story "The Night-Born" is that a person must strive to achieve happiness. Furthermore, the story emphasized despite obstacles, people should always strive to pursue their dreams.

The strength and patience of women are demonstrated, showing how Uzbek women like Malohatkxon, despite their husbands' unemployment, did not feel embarrassed from hard work and determination to support their families. The story promotes ideas of loyalty and faithfulness towards one's husband. Since the story is based on real-life events, it leaves a strong impression on the reader.

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